

Continually learn to map visual concepts to language models in resource-constrained environments

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HIGHLIGHTS

- A small visual model can be trained with knowledge space created by a frozen LM.
- CVM improves performance and mitigating forgetting in standard benchmarks.
- We study the generalization and transfer capabilities of our proposal.
- CL method based on a large pre-trained model fails in fine-grained datasets.
- CVM achieves similar results with lower inference time in fine-grained datasets.

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ABSTRACT

Continually learning from non-independent and identically distributed (non-i.i.d.) data poses a significant challenge in deep learning, particularly in resource-constrained environments. Visual models trained via supervised learning often suffer from overfitting, catastrophic forgetting, and biased representations when faced with sequential tasks. In contrast, pre-trained language models demonstrate greater robustness in managing task sequences due to their generalized knowledge representations, albeit at the cost of high computational resources. Leveraging this advantage, we propose a novel learning strategy, Continual Visual Mapping (CVM), which continuously maps visual representations into a fixed knowledge space derived from a language model. By anchoring learning to this fixed space, CVM enables training small, efficient visual models, making it particularly suited for scenarios where adapting large pre-trained visual models is computationally or data-prohibitive. Empirical evaluations across five benchmarks demonstrate that CVM consistently outperforms state-of-the-art continual learning methods, showcasing its potential to enhance generalization and mitigate challenges in resource-constrained continual learning settings.

1. Introduction

Increasing the amount of training data has repeatedly shown significant impacts on the performance of deep learning models [1,2]. Generally speaking, as the quality and diversity of the training set expand, the performance of the predictive models increases—a trend that is particularly pronounced with *Transformer* architectures [3], which has uncovered new models capable of achieving state-of-the-art performance in multiple tasks, such as textual [2], visual [4] and

multiple modalities [5], provided that the necessary amount of data is available.

Transformers have demonstrated impressive performance, developing a wide range of large pre-trained models. These collections of models are particularly beneficial for individuals or organizations that do not have the resources or data to train large models from scratch. However, some level of fine-tuning is usually necessary to adapt these models to perform correctly in specific tasks. Given that fine-tuning these models

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requires significant amounts of data and computational power, much effort has been directed toward improving their ability to transfer their knowledge effectively to different domains [6,7].

Their ability to adapt to multiple domains has made them relevant in scenarios where learning different classes continuously is necessary. These scenarios are known as Continual Learning (CL). By fixing the pre-trained weights and using their internal knowledge, many proposed CL methods have achieved state-of-the-art results in various settings [8–10]. However, continually adapting or fine-tuning large pre-trained models is computationally expensive and becomes impractical, or even *not possible* in resource-constrained environments, where we must keep resource use low. These restrictions are especially relevant when the model obtains the prediction for new samples (*inference*), as this can hardly be done offline.

The challenge of employing large models in resource-constrained environments raises the question: *Can we use the knowledge of large pre-trained models without directly employing them in training and inference on continual learning scenarios?*

In this study, we propose the creation of a knowledge space by leveraging feature vectors extracted from a fixed, pre-trained Language Model (LM). Each vector corresponds to a distinct concept derived from the available data. This approach is advantageous because, unlike models trained on a limited set of classes, pre-trained LM vectors encapsulate a global understanding of concepts. This phenomenon is due to the diverse and extensive data used during pre-training, enabling the model to capture relationships among concepts present in the current data and among those that may emerge in future tasks. For instance, vectors representing animal-related concepts are expected to cluster closer than those representing unrelated concepts, such as a *car*.

To leverage this knowledge space, we propose utilizing only the vectors extracted from a *frozen* LM while training a small visual model with these vectors serving as anchors. Each anchor represents a class in the current task. This approach enables efficient training and deployment of the model in resource-constrained environments. Our focus on LMs is motivated by three main reasons: i) LMs inherently define rich and robust semantic spaces that can be repurposed across diverse tasks [11]; ii) LMs are rapidly advancing and are generally more accessible (often open-source) compared to visual or multi-modal models [12]; and iii)

LMs establish a direct connection between textual labels in visually supervised datasets and the corresponding linguistic concepts, facilitating seamless integration of textual and conceptual information.

Hence, our approach focuses on training small visual models that can map their representations to a conceptual space established by an LM, replacing the classifier with a distance function between the representations obtained from the visual model and the anchors extracted from the LM. Similar to CLIP [5], we propose a multi-modal approach. However, instead of continually training the text and visual transformer together, we obtain the representation from a frozen LM and train only a small visual model to map the visual representations to this knowledgeable latent space. Hopefully, the visual model will learn the semantic information from the fixed latent space. We call this approach *Continual Visual Mapping (CVM)*, and a visual representation can be found in Fig. 1.

This approach is highly relevant in CL for two main reasons. Firstly, substituting the linear classifier with a stable set of anchor vectors eliminates interference generated in the classification layer, a recognized contributor to forgetting [13,14]. Secondly, we expect the visual model to learn more general visual representations that will transfer better to future tasks, which can increase forward transfer capabilities.

This study demonstrates the performance of the proposed method in class-incremental and domain-incremental learning. Also, it highlights the limitations of current CL methods that rely on fixed pre-trained visual models. These existing methods struggle with tasks that include data outside the pre-trained distribution, often resulting in worse performance than our proposed CVM. Furthermore, by training a smaller visual model, CVM significantly enhances inference speed, making it well-suited for real-time applications. The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- We propose a CL method that trains a compact visual model by aligning its representations with a knowledge space derived from a frozen LM (Section 3.2). This approach improves performance and mitigates forgetting on standard benchmarks (Section 4.2).
- We evaluate the generalization and transfer capabilities of our method, demonstrating favorable results compared to other CL approaches (Section 5).

Fig. 1. Conceptual image of our continual visual mapping (CVM) method. A small and efficient parametric model f_θ is continually learned to map its visual concepts into semantically richer embeddings seldom extracted from frozen and pre-trained language models (LMs).

- We conduct experiments on fine-grained datasets where methods relying on large, pre-trained visual models under-perform. Our results show that CVM achieves comparable performance while significantly reducing inference time, compared to approaches that directly utilize large models during training (Section 5.1).

The organization of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a brief overview of related work in Continual Learning and Multi-Modal representations. Section 3 outlines the background, the Continual Learning framework we will utilize, and the details of how CVM operates. In Section 4, we compare our proposed model with similar approaches, together with analyzing the most critical components of our approach through an ablation study. Section 5 presents an analysis of the generalization capabilities of different methods, including a study where methods based on large pre-trained models may fail. Finally, Section 6 presents the conclusions and a summary of the paper.

2. Related work

2.1. Continual learning

Continual learning (CL) in deep learning [15–17] focuses on training a sequence of tasks continuously. This approach can benefit applications ranging from robotics [18] to style transfer [19]. However, the ongoing adjustment of model weights can lead to an issue known as *Catastrophic Forgetting*, where the model forgets previously learned tasks. Most CL methods can be categorized into various non-exclusive approaches. These include subdividing model parameters into subspaces for each new task [20,21], imposing constraints on learned gradients [22,23], and employing meta-learning to develop reusable weights for all tasks [24,25]. Among these methods, memory-based approaches, such as Experience Replay (ER) [26,27], offer a straightforward solution that has demonstrated promising results. Memory-based methods tackle catastrophic forgetting by incorporating data from previous tasks into the training process for the current task [28,29]. They have consistently achieved state-of-the-art performance on most benchmarks by effectively mitigating forgetting through the continuous repetition of previous tasks.

Applying large pre-trained models in CL has improved performance across several downstream tasks [8–10,30]. This improvement arises from their ability to leverage pre-trained representations, which significantly aid in mitigating the challenges of catastrophic forgetting. These models are trained on extensive datasets, enabling them to develop valuable representations for various modalities and inputs [4,31]. As a result, they serve as an excellent foundation for CL solutions. However, their massive parameter count and the requirement for substantial data access render them impractical for continual training as new data distributions emerge [32].

2.2. Learning multi-modal representations

Training predictive models that connect different data modalities—such as vision, text, and speech—has yielded richer and more reusable representations in deep learning [2]. One of the most well-known multi-modal models is CLIP [5], which trains visual and language representations to create a common latent space where the visual and textual representations of the same input are closely aligned. This key insight has been further refined and expanded [33–35], achieving state-of-the-art performance across various tasks [36]. Other works have explored how transferable visual representations are when using different textual supervision [37].

Pioneering works [38–40] have examined the training of visual models using static language representations, predating the development of contextualized embeddings and large language models. Unlike these previous studies, our approach leverages extracted contextual information. Specifically, we establish a knowledge framework based on pre-trained

language models, with the expectation that this will enhance our visual model by incorporating the semantic knowledge contained within these language models. Additionally, we explore how this method can help reduce forgetting in continual learning scenarios by integrating a retention loss. This loss function is designed to minimize the loss of semantic knowledge from previously learned tasks. Ultimately, our solution offers a resource-efficient alternative to employing large pre-trained models.

3. Methodology

3.1. Background

In supervised CL, we consider a stream of T tasks. Each task t consists of a new data distribution $D^t = (X^t, Y^t)$, where X^t denotes the input instances and Y^t denotes the instance labels. The goal is to train a classification model $f_\theta : X \rightarrow Y$ using data from a sequence of T tasks: $D = \{D^1, \dots, D^T\}$. During each task, model f_θ will minimize the objective function \mathcal{L} using data D^t .

$$\mathcal{L}(D^t) = \frac{1}{N^t} \sum_{i=1}^{N^t} \mathcal{L}_t(f_\theta(x_i^t), y_i^t) \quad (1)$$

Each task is presented sequentially to the model and trained for E epochs. This work focuses on the traditional *Class-Incremental (Class-IL)* setting. This scenario is often intended as the most challenging in CL [41]. Unlike *Task Incremental Learning (Task-IL)*, in Class-IL, a task descriptor is only available during training. To verify the generality of our proposal, we also run experiments in a *Domain Incremental (Domain-IL)* setting, where each task considers all classes but the distribution of each class changes over time.

A popular family of methods to tackle CL is known as memory-based methods. Here, together with minimizing Eq. (1), model f_θ needs to minimize \mathcal{L} using the data available in the buffer memory M at time t . The buffer M^t comprises $|M|$ samples from previous distributions, meaning that at task t , the buffer will contain a limited set of samples collected from tasks $t' < t$.

$$\mathcal{L}_M(D^t, M^t) = \mathcal{L}(D^t) + \frac{1}{|M|} \sum_{i=1}^{|M|} \mathcal{L}_t(f_\theta(m_i^t), y_i^t) \quad (2)$$

Instead of concatenating the datasets D^t and M^t , which could neglect the representativeness of the memory, some works have adopted the concatenation of current data and memory at the batch level [42]. In this work, we follow this approach, which has been shown to increase the performance of memory-based methods.

3.2. Continual visual mapping (CVM)

In a classic formulation of a classification problem, a model f_θ is composed of a feature extractor f_θ and a classifier c_ω , where θ and ω are the trainable weights of the model f_θ . During training, the learning strategy simultaneously tries to learn robust, semantic vector representations of the input (f_θ) and a classifier (c_ω) that uses these vectors to discriminate between the classes, ideally generalizing to samples not seen during training. With this, the prediction \hat{y}_i for the input x_i is obtained as follows:

$$\hat{y}_i = c_\omega(f_\theta(x_i)) \quad (3)$$

In CL, the constant modification of the weights θ and ω results in ongoing interference between tasks. This interference can induce forgetting, which causes a decrease in the overall performance of previously seen classes. We hypothesize that this interference is primarily due to the biases and boundaries the model learns during a task, primarily due to the limited amount of information the model sees during each task—knowledge that may become unsuitable for future distributions.

One challenge in CL is that visual models must learn from a limited world perspective. When presented with a sequence of tasks, the model tends to focus only on the characteristics of the current task without considering the context of past and future classes. This restricted view can result in the model developing biases based on the distribution of the current task. These factors strongly restrict the transferability of the learned representations to future tasks due to bias, making them prone to overfitting and less reusable. Intuitively, the differences a model can learn when comparing *Cat* and *Plane* should be different when we know (or do not know) the existence of other animals.

Identifying that this narrow representation of the world model is given by the limited diversity of classes in the current task, our method proposes replacing the classifier c_w with a set of fixed *anchor vectors*, one for each class of the current task. These vectors are extracted from a pre-trained LM, creating a fixed and knowledgeable latent space that encapsulates the knowledge and relationships the LM has about the task classes.

By changing the classification layer with a knowledgeable latent space, we expect to encourage the trainable model f_θ to learn representations that inculcate some of the semantic information in their internal representations. With this modification, we expect to (1) leverage the knowledgeable space created by the anchor vector to guide the training of the visual model and (2) increase the transferability of the visual representations.

When a new task D' arrives during training, we extract the textual representation for each class, creating a latent space imbued with a broad understanding of the world [43]. Given the absence of textual descriptions for images in most visual datasets, we generate a text vector C_c for each class c , using the prompt “This is an image of” + *label*, where *label* represents the text associated with each class (i.e., the class name). This prompt follows the CLIP approach [5]. As a common practice, to extract the vector, we input it to the LM and extract the [CLS] representation just before the classifier of the pre-trained model. Notably, the LM is not employed during training, as our focus is solely on obtaining fixed vectors to replace the classifier. This strategy can be easily implemented in resource-constrained environments as a *one-time query* to an external service.

To train the visual model, we use a Triplet Loss [44] with the anchor corresponding to the correct class as a positive vector and another random anchor as a negative. We use this loss since it balances bringing the representation of an image closer to the corresponding anchor vector, but at the same time, it seeks to keep the generated vectors of different classes away from each other:

$$L_m = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \max(0, d(f_\theta(x_i), C_i^P) - d(f_\theta(x_i), C_i^N) + \alpha) \quad (4)$$

As shown in Eq. (4), the objective is to minimize the distance d between the feature vector $f_\theta(x_i)$ and the representation of the

corresponding class in the latent space C_i^P , while concurrently increasing the distance between $f_\theta(x_i)$ and negative classes. Here, α is the margin of the triplet loss and was set to 0.1 empirically. We employ the cosine distance in all our experiments.

This strategy aims to train the visual model to map its representations to a fixed latent space created with knowledge extracted from an LM, thereby aligning both sources of information. This integration forms the basis of our approach, which we term Continual Visual Mapping (CVM). We encourage the visual model to learn relations extracted from the LM using these vectors as anchors. We expect that we can mitigate forgetting by having a fixed anchor space instead of a learnable classification layer.

In addition to mapping visual representations to the knowledge space, we expect the visual model to grasp semantic information, specifically the relationships between classes. This knowledge acquisition is anticipated to enhance the generalization capabilities of the visual model, facilitated by the knowledge of the anchor vectors. However, one issue with the current proposal is that the loss function L_m operates under the assumption that all classes exhibit the same semantic distance, overlooking potential similarities between classes that share common characteristics and knowledge, such as the similarity between dogs and cats compared to planes.

To address this issue, we introduce a novel loss function designed to consider previous similarities learned by the model. Our proposal involves preserving the distances between classes encountered in the past, aiming to maintain some semantics of earlier tasks. To achieve this, we compute the distance between the representations of input x_i and all previous classes $C^{<t}$ using both the current model f_{θ^t} and the model at time $t-1$.

$$L_d = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i d(d(f_{\theta^t}(x_i), C^{<t}), d(f_{\theta^{t-1}}(x_i), C^{<t})) \quad (5)$$

As shown in Eq. (5), our objective is to minimize the discrepancy between currently learned distances $d(d(f_{\theta^t}(x_i), C^{<t}))$ and those learned by a previous version of the model $d(f_{\theta^{t-1}}(x_i), C^{<t})$, thereby incorporating past similarities into the learning process. It is worth noting that we only compare against classes seen before the current experiences ($< t$) to maintain the alignment in the learned space.

Finally, we combine both losses according to Eq. (6). We add a coefficient β to control how much the model needs to remember previously learned distances between classes.

$$L_t = L_m + \beta L_d \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2(a) visually represents the training loss. When the model learns new classes (*boat* and *plane*), L_m minimizes the distance between $f_{\theta^t}(x_i)$ and the corresponding anchor vector while increasing the distance between that same vector and other classes (full line). On the other hand, L_d aims to reduce the difference between past task relationships by using only data from the current task (dotted line).

Fig. 2. Diagram of how CVM works at training and inference. During training (a), when adding new classes (plane and boat), two losses are involved: the triplet loss with a margin α (Eq. 4) and the semantic distance loss restrained by coefficient β (Eq. 5). At inference (b), the prediction \hat{Y} is obtained by selecting the minimum distance between the image embedding and the seen classes in the latent space.

During inference, when the model is trained, and all class representations C are generated, we obtain the corresponding class of x_i by finding the most similar anchor vector with cosine similarity.

$$\hat{Y}_i = \min(d(f_\theta(x_i), C)) \quad (7)$$

As shown in Eq. (7), we compare the visual representations of the image x_i with the known vectors in the latent space and select the nearest class. It is important to note that at time t , C is composed only of seen classes. Fig. 2(b) shows how the model works during test time, where each arrow represents the distance between the image x_i and the corresponding class anchor.

4. Experiments

To showcase the effectiveness of CVM, we have empirically assessed it in various scenarios and benchmarks traditionally used in CL.

4.1. Implementation details

For the visual model, we use a reduced version of a ResNet-18 architecture proposed in [45], as one of our objectives is to simulate a resource-constrained environment. For a fair comparison, all baselines use the same model, where the only difference between the model used in CVM and other baselines is that we replace the classifier with anchor vectors in our approach. This modification causes CVM to train fewer parameters as it uses a fixed latent space. For the LM, we use SentenceBERT [46] to extract the textual representation for the classes. We ran all the experiments with three different seeds, each inducing a different ordering of the sequences of tasks.

We compare our proposal to different types of CL methods. First, we compare our proposal against some classic regularization-based CL methods like AGEM [47], EWC [22], and LwF [48]. We also compare against memory-based methods like ER [42], DER [49], and iCarl [45]. iCarl is especially interesting in our case since it also removes the classifier at inference time. However, the methods differ mainly in training, as iCarl uses a cross-entropy loss with labels instead of a Triplet loss with distance to knowledge anchor vectors. The way iCarl generates the vector per class is also different since the vectors are generated based on samples in the memory.

We tested all methods in a Class-IL scenario using CIFAR100 [50] and Tiny-ImageNet [51] datasets. We split these datasets into 10 experiences, each with an equal number of new classes, 10 and 20, respectively. We also run experiments in a Domain-IL scenario and higher-dimensional input spaces using the more realistic CORE50 dataset [52], designed explicitly for embedded continual object recognition applications. Here, the setting comprises 10 domestic objects, and each new experience imposes a new class distribution (e.g., background, illumination, occlusion, scale, among others).

In all experiments, we use an SGD optimizer with a learning rate of 0.1 and a batch size of 32. CIFAR100 and TinyImagenet train for 50 epochs per experience; for CORE50, we train for 30 epochs. We use the implementation provided by Avalanche [53] for benchmarks and methods. We used the hyperparameters proposed by the authors in the corresponding paper. The code of CVM will become available upon acceptance.

For evaluation metrics, we use the average accuracy (Acc) and forgetting (For) over the T tasks after the sequential learning as proposed in [23]. Eqs. (8) and (9) show the formulas for accuracy and forgetting, respectively, where $Acc_{i,j}$ is the accuracy of task i after training on task j .

$$Acc = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T Acc_{T,i} \quad (8)$$

$$For = \frac{1}{T-1} \sum_{i=1}^{T-1} Acc_{T,i} - Acc_{i,i} \quad (9)$$

4.2. Results

Table 1 provides the results for Class-IL benchmarks. As previous studies have shown, regularization methods are suboptimal in this scenario. However, performance gains can be achieved by leveraging access to previous tasks stored in a buffer, exemplified by methods ER and DER. Additionally, combining EWC with classical ER only seems to increase performance in Tiny-ImageNet.

To start testing our proposal, we replace the Cross-Entropy Loss in ER, ER + EWC, and DER with the mapping loss presented in Eq. (4). This ablation shows the positive effect of replacing the classification layer with anchors extracted from an LM. The table shows that this strategy significantly increases accuracy, particularly in ER + EWC, where the accuracy increases by 6 %. The model gains valuable insights by incorporating additional information from the latent representations, which is particularly advantageous in CL scenarios where knowledgeable representations can enhance generalization. However, it is noteworthy that this transferability is most pronounced in simple benchmarks like CIFAR100. In contrast, on more complex benchmarks such as Tiny-ImageNet and CORE50, L_m does not improve performance in previous methods.

The low performance of Tiny-ImageNet can be attributed to the significant increase in forgetting compared to CIFAR100. As expected, when we increase the complexity of the relationships between the classes, using only the anchor vector is not enough to mitigate forgetting and improve performance.

To help mitigate the forgetting, we add the novel loss L_d . This loss is specifically crafted to influence the distances between classes, acknowledging that certain classes are more similar than others, which is not considered in the traditional triplet loss. Combining this loss with L_m creates CVM, which aims to extract valuable knowledge from the latent space while preserving the inherent class relationships. As detailed in Table 1, our experimental results confirm that the combination of L_m and L_d outperforms previous methods, including iCarl, which also removes the classifier during inference. These findings highlight that **relying solely on information extraction from an LM is insufficient**, emphasizing the necessity of incorporating additional mechanisms to work in CL scenarios.

Similar results can be seen in a Domain-IL scenario, as shown in Table 1. Most regularization techniques find it challenging to perform well, and memory-based methods produce the best results. iCarl, despite being a memory-based method, also faces difficulties due to the constant shift in the class distribution. Here, introducing L_m does not aid ER or DER in enhancing their outcomes. However, CVM still surpasses its predecessors by encouraging the reuse of previous distances.

4.3. Ablation

In CL, there is a constant trade-off between plasticity and stability. On the one hand, preserving the plasticity of the model is fundamental to learning new tasks and distributions, modifying the weights that cause forgetting. On the other hand, increasing stability can decrease forgetting, but it will decrease the option to learn a new task. This trade-off between learning new classes and forgetting previous ones is the primary concern that most CL methods face.

4.3.1. Memory size

In memory-based methods, the trade-off is addressed by adding a memory buffer that continuously repeats samples of previous tasks. Increasing the memory size improves the representativeness of the buffer, which should increase performance by decreasing forgetting. As shown in Table 2, DER is the method that scales the best as we increase the buffer size, significantly increasing its performance; however, it still achieves lower results than CVM, which consistently outperforms previous methods. On the other hand, iCarl scales poorly.

Something that explains the low performance of iCarl is plasticity. As shown in Table 1, iCarl obtained a lower forgetting value. These results

Table 1

Accuracy and forgetting for CIFAR100, Tiny-ImageNet, and CORE50. CVM outperforms all methods regarding average accuracy due to the combination of L_m and the semantic loss. We cannot measure the forgetting metric in CORE50 since it is designed with a unique and fixed test set.

	Class-IL				Domain-IL
	CIFAR100		Tiny-ImageNet		CORE50
	Acc	For	Acc	For	Acc
Naive	9.0 % \pm 1.7	78.6 % \pm 0.8	7.4 % \pm 0.1	73.9 % \pm 0.3	23.1 % \pm 1.0
AGEM	9.3 % \pm 0.9	77.8 % \pm 0.3	7.5 % \pm 0.1	74.7 % \pm 0.3	26.0 % \pm 1.3
LWF	8.8 % \pm 1.5	76.3 % \pm 1.0	7.4 % \pm 0.0	73.0 % \pm 0.4	31.7 % \pm 2.2
EWC	8.6 % \pm 0.2	77.7 % \pm 0.7	7.3 % \pm 0.1	70.7 % \pm 0.6	24.0 % \pm 3.4
ER	21.0 % \pm 0.1	65.0 % \pm 0.7	13.1 % \pm 0.2	65.8 % \pm 0.2	33.0 % \pm 0.4
ER + L_m	20.9 % \pm 0.7	64.7 % \pm 0.5	10.7 % \pm 0.3	66.2 % \pm 0.6	32.8 % \pm 1.3
ER + EWC	19.2 % \pm 0.4	64.8 % \pm 0.7	17.7 % \pm 1.0	55.5 % \pm 0.6	31.9 % \pm 0.1
ER + EWC + L_m	25.2 % \pm 0.6	51.9 % \pm 0.2	11.5 % \pm 1.2	58.7 % \pm 0.8	32.2 % \pm 2.3
DER	19.1 % \pm 0.8	65.3 % \pm 0.1	13.9 % \pm 0.4	64.1 % \pm 0.7	34.8 % \pm 2.3
DER + L_m	21.0 % \pm 1.2	64.4 % \pm 0.6	11.7 % \pm 0.4	64.9 % \pm 0.5	33.1 % \pm 0.6
iCarl	29.1 % \pm 1.1	23.2 % \pm 0.2	24.3 % \pm 0.2	16.2 % \pm 0.1	17.8 % \pm 1.8
CVM	32.9 % \pm0.4	40.1 % \pm0.8	27.0 % \pm0.8	33.9 % \pm0.8	37.6 % \pm1.1

Table 2

We use the CIFAR100 benchmark to test the performance with different memory sizes. Methods scale differently; iCarl does not scale well, increasing only 10 %, while DER increases performance quite a bit (31 %). CVM still outperforms it in every scenario.

	Memory size				
	500	1000	2000	3000	5000
ER	21.0 %	28.2 %	36.8 %	40.5 %	47.3 %
ER + L_m	20.9 %	27.9 %	37.7 %	41.8 %	47.3 %
ER + EWC	19.2 %	26.1 %	35.0 %	39.4 %	43.6 %
ER + EWC + L_m	25.2 %	26.1 %	35.5 %	39.1 %	46.8 %
DER	19.1 %	26.6 %	39.3 %	45.3 %	50.9 %
DER + L_m	21.0 %	28.2 %	39.6 %	43.1 %	47.5 %
iCarl	29.1 %	36.4 %	37.7 %	38.8 %	39.6 %
CVM	32.9 %	38.7 %	43.5 %	47.5 %	51.4 %

can be explained by the significant restrictions that iCarl imposes when training new tasks. These constraints become more evident as we increase the memory size. iCarl can maintain a lower level of forgetfulness, but at the cost of having low plasticity and being unable to scale up when we increase memory size. In contrast, CVM has no problem scaling up and maintaining a high level of plasticity.

We present two compelling arguments affirming the effectiveness of CVM and the importance of the proposed learning strategy for CL. Firstly, our approach involves mapping visual representations to a stable and well-informed space, removing the need for a classifier. Previous studies highlight the classifier as a critical contributor to model overfitting, particularly in challenging CL environments [13]. This finding gains further support from the insights in Table 2, where enhancing memory representativeness enhances overall performance and mitigates the risk of overfitting to limited memory capacities. Secondly, the strategic alignment of concepts in the latent space is crucial. The semantic information within the space generated by a frozen LM discerns the similarities among diverse classes. This concept is actively promoted by incorporating the loss described in Eq. (5).

To validate our hypotheses, Fig. 3 presents the evolution of the confusion matrices for iCaRL, DER, and CVM as memory size increases. The diagonal elements remain visible in all cases, primarily indicating correct classifications. However, identifying where the models make errors is crucial for understanding their limitations.

For iCaRL, errors are spread across all classes under a low-memory budget. As the memory size increases, performance improves slightly, but the model begins to overfit, resulting in predictions concentrated within a small subset of classes. In contrast, DER exhibits a strong tendency to classify images into specific classes when memory is limited,

as evidenced by prominent columns in the confusion matrix. As the memory capacity increases, these errors become more evenly distributed across classes. DER’s plasticity can partially explain this behavior: with limited memory, the model is more prone to forgetting (as reflected by the concentrated columns). Conversely, increasing the memory reduces the number and concentration of errors, but still, the top 5 most predicted classes concentrate 2500 of the predictions compared to only 1500 of CVM.

One of the motivations for removing the classifier in our method is to mitigate overfitting to specific classes. As shown in Fig. 3(c) and (f), CVM effectively addresses this issue in low- and high-memory settings. The absence of a strong preference for specific classes suggests that our approach is more robust across memory configurations.

Nonetheless, a key concern when training with a contextual representation space is whether the visual model can capture fine-grained semantic distinctions and does not confuse semantically similar classes. One way to assess this is by analyzing the most frequently predicted classes. The classes “shark” and “tractor” were the most commonly predicted in CVM. Misclassifications associated with “shark” included “skunk,” “bottle,” and “bus,” while “tractor” was confused with “castle,” “bicycle,” and “road.” In both cases, there was no clear tendency to confuse semantically similar classes, suggesting that the visual model is learning a meaningful semantic space, and that the confusion could come from the visual part.

Despite outperforming previous models, distinguishing visually similar classes remains challenging. In future work, we aim to enhance the textual representation by exploring richer prompts and alternative data augmentation strategies, especially approaches that remain computationally efficient.

4.3.2. CVM components

A critical component of CVM is the coefficient β of Equation L_r , which controls the importance of keeping the relation between previous classes. As shown in Fig. 4(a), the optimal value is strongly related to the memory size. As we increase the memory size, the model can repeat more concepts presented in the buffer, which decreases the need to remember the exact distance of previous tasks, meaning that CVM can work with a smaller β . On the other hand, if we decrease the memory size, the model must depend mainly on the loss function to maintain the semantic knowledge learned in the past.

The second experiment about β concerns the plasticity of the model. As shown in Fig. 4, the accuracy of the last task decreases as we increase the β coefficient. This result is explained by discouragement in moving weights when training for a new task, reducing plasticity. With a high value of β , the loss promotes fewer modifications to the model weights, reducing forgetting but decreasing the final accuracy.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix of iCarl, DER, and CVM with 1000 and 5000 memory size in CIFAR100. This benchmark has 100 elements per class in the test set. Ideally, the diagonal should be as close as possible to the 100 value, and the rest of the matrix should be zero.

Fig. 4. Ablation study over the β coefficient. Intuitively, β controls how much to consider past distances, impacting performance. In Fig. 4(a), it is shown that the optimal coefficient tends to decrease as we increase the memory size since memory provides a better representation of past distributions. On the other side, β controls the plasticity of a model. Fig. 4(b) shows the accuracy of the last task. Increasing β encourages the model to maintain previous semantic knowledge while decreasing plasticity.

Another critical component of CVM is the LM, which creates the fixed latent space. Maintaining the prompt fixed, we compare SentenceBERT with CLIP and BERT textual models. Results are shown in Table 3. These results show that using an appropriate model to generate the latent space is essential. It is important to note that a more complex and complete model can be used; however, only medium models were used due to computational restrictions. Future work will explore using more detailed

descriptions or concepts extracted from the image instead of directly using the class.

One possible limitation of CVM is that we assume that LMs are trained with enough data to contain all the classes we can use. We know that new classes that will not be included in the models may be created. However, the speed with which more complex and data-intensive models are trained can mitigate this limitation. As we show,

Table 3

The knowledgeable space created by the LM is critical for CVM. As the performance of these models grows, our method should obtain a better approximation of a semantic space. Here, we test different LMs from which to extract the world representation.

	SentenceBERT	Text CLIP	BERT
Acc	32.9 % \pm 0.4	31.0 % \pm 0.2	29.8 % \pm 0.6

CVM is independent of the model language used, and one with better representations can further improve performance.

5. Generalization capabilities

For continual learners to be efficient, they should reuse previous knowledge when learning new tasks. It is hypothesized that reusing previous knowledge could mitigate forgetting since the model would have no incentive to modify that knowledge. On this note, an essential feature in CL models is the generalization ability due to their transfer capability to *future tasks*.

There are two distinct approaches to assessing the transfer capability of a model. The first approach involves freezing the model and training a linear classifier (linear probing) on unseen classes. This evaluation method measures the generality of the representations acquired by the model for future tasks. The second approach focuses on evaluating the zero-shot capabilities of the model. CVM involves incorporating an anchor vector of unseen classes and verifying the accuracy exclusively for those classes while keeping the visual model frozen. This method provides insights into the model's ability to classify classes not part of the training set.

In the first approach, reusable representations indicate how prepared a model is to learn new tasks. A low value in accuracy suggests that the model should highly modify its representation to learn new tasks; conversely, a higher accuracy value indicates that minor modifications are needed to adjust to new tasks. The results of applying the linear probing are shown in Fig. 5(a). The results indicate that the learned representations of CVM have the highest transfer capabilities, ranging from 16 % when compared with 90 unseen classes (after training the first task) to about 22 % when only 10 classes remain. In contrast, iCarL fails to generate good representations, as it has close to random values, which the low plasticity can explain.

The zero-shot capabilities take the previous observation to an extreme. If a model can learn to identify a class without modifying its weights, it learns the new distribution without forgetting. However,

Table 4

The FW_{Score} is a metric that helps compare the transfer capacity of different CL methods. CVM outperforms previous methods of learning representations that learn unseen classes using two approaches.

	Random	ER	DER	iCarL	CVM
FW_{Score}	3.1 %	11.2 %	8.9 %	5.9 %	18.4 %
Zero-shot acc.	3.1 %	–	–	–	7.9 %

methods with a classifier are limited to the classes seen due to constraints in how the classifier is optimized and structured. In contrast, CVM holds a distinct advantage. By relying on a distance metric instead of a trained classifier, CVM can classify classes not encountered during training by adding an anchor vector that represents the textual description of the new class. In this context, the zero-shot accuracy performance of the model is computed on unseen classes for tasks $t' > t$ when t is the current task. Results are illustrated in Fig. 5. It is noteworthy that methods with a classifier exhibit a performance of 0 % due to the inherent limitations of the classifier.

Unlike accuracy, where the final value represents how accurately methods perform, the transfer capabilities are better measured over the complete sequence. We developed a simple scoring system to easily compare the transfer capabilities between various methods. This score is obtained by averaging the accuracy achieved by each metric after completing each task. For instance, in the case of linear probing, we train a linear classifier (f_{γ}^t) after each task (t), using only data from unseen tasks ($t' > t$), i.e., $X^{t'>t}$ and $Y^{t'>t}$. This score helps us understand how well the method performs on unseen classes. We average all these performances, as shown in Eq. (10).

$$FW_{score} = \frac{1}{T-1} \sum_{t=1}^{T-1} Acc(f_{\gamma}^t, X^{t'>t}, Y^{t'>t}) \quad (10)$$

A higher value means that the representations learnt during the sequence are more capable of being used in future tasks. The results of the score for each method can be found in Table 4.

5.1. Limitations of pre-trained models

Most proposed methods that tackle CL problems are based on pre-trained models. These methods keep the model weights fixed and only add modifications such as soft prompts. However, even in scenarios where we have ample computational power to use these models, other issues can arise that make methods based on large visual pre-trained models unsuitable, e.g., the need for more data, the specificity, or even the granularity of the problem.

Fig. 5. Using CIFAR100, we evaluate the approaches over unseen tasks, meaning that after Task 0, we have 90 unseen classes. Fig. 5(a) shows the accuracy when freezing the model and learning a linear classifier with the unseen classes after training each task. Random denotes a random assignment of classes. Fig. 5(b) shows the accuracy of the zero-shot performance of CVM compared to a random classification. After training task t , we test the zero-shot capabilities on classes of tasks $t' > t$ and compare them with randomly assigned classes. Random assignment can be estimated as: $1/|\text{unseen}|$.

Table 5

Two CL benchmarks are proposed with granular datasets. In these benchmarks, visual models outperform CL methods based on large pre-trained models in terms of accuracy and inference time.

	GTSRB		Aircraft	
	Acc	Inf. time	Acc	Inf. time
L2P	32.4 % \pm 0.4	\sim 188 s	34.0 % \pm 3.7	\sim 100 s
L2P + ER	74.9 % \pm 4.1	\sim 188 s	34.9 % \pm 1.3	\sim 100 s
ER	79.4 % \pm 0.2	\sim 14 s	35.0 % \pm 1.6	\sim 65 s
DER	83.6 % \pm 1.4	\sim 14 s	36.1 % \pm 2.3	\sim 65 s
CVM	84.8 % \pm1.3	\sim 14 s	36.5 % \pm1.1	\sim 65 s

Table 6

CLIP was trained with a large data source, which helps it achieve good zero-shot performance on various tasks. However, performance drops when the task distributions are very different from those used in training.

	CIFAR100	GTSRB	Aircraft
Zero-shot CLIP B/32	65.1 %	32.2 %	21.2 %
Zero-shot CLIP L/14	77.9 %	50.3 %	36.1 %
Linear CLIP B/32	95.1 %	85.3 %	52.0 %
Linear CLIP L/14	98.0 %	92.5 %	69.4 %
CVM	51.4 %	84.8 %	36.5 %

We introduce two CL benchmarks to compare the plasticity capabilities against methods that keep pre-trained weights fixed. We utilize GTSRB [54] and Aircraft [55] datasets. For the GTSRB dataset, we delineate 10 tasks, while the Aircraft dataset is partitioned into five tasks, both adhering to a Class-IL scenario.

The primary challenge confronted by methods relying on pre-trained models arises from the granularity of the dataset. This fine-grained nature necessitates additional information not present in the weights of large pre-trained models. Consequently, pre-trained models require assistance to learn the sequence, leading to low performance. In Table 5, we present the performance of L2P [9] both with and without memory. Notably, these approaches fail to outperform methods employing simpler models. Although pre-trained models may perform similarly to simpler and smaller models, their longer inference times can adversely impact overall performance.

One advantage of large pre-trained models is that they are trained on large and diverse datasets, enabling them to create representations that generalize to various tasks. Even in scenarios where training is not feasible due to limited training data or resource constraints, these large pre-trained models can perform well using zero-shot learning. This is evident in the results for CIFAR100 in Table 6, where CLIP outperforms CVM without requiring any training. However, when the input data distribution differs significantly from the pre-training set, these pre-trained models often fail to perform well in zero-shot context due to a lack of internal knowledge. This issue is highlighted in fine-grained benchmarks, such as Aircraft and GTSRB, where CVM significantly outperforms zero-shot CLIP due to its specific understanding of the current distribution. If we train CLIP on the entire dataset (the upper bound for CL), it can outperform CVM, but this comes with a higher training cost and substantial inference costs, which can be prohibitive in low-resource environments.

6. Conclusions

In this work, we introduced Continual Visual Mapping (CVM), a novel approach that leverages a conceptual latent space generated by a frozen language model (LM) to train a compact visual model. By learning to map visual representations into this knowledgeable space, the visual model gains the ability to acquire new concepts by building on the pre-learned textual information encoded in the LM. We evaluate CVM in both class-incremental and domain-incremental learning scenarios using diverse benchmarks, demonstrating state-of-the-art performance in

resource-constrained environments. Notably, we identify cases where small and simple models prove more efficient and surpass the effectiveness of methods relying on large pre-trained models, particularly in settings where the low transferability of such models hampers their performance. This learning strategy introduces a new direction for continual learning research, enabling asynchronous and efficient integration of knowledge from large pre-trained models while effectively mapping new knowledge to existing representations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Clea Rebillard: Methodology, Conceptualization, Visualization, Formal analysis. **Julio Hurtado:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Formal analysis. **Andrii Kruttsylo:** Formal analysis, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Lucia Passaro:** Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Formal analysis. **Vincenzo Lomonaco:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization, Visualization, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Lucia Passaro reports that financial support was provided by European Commission. Vincenzo Lomonaco reports that financial support was provided by European Commission. Lucia Passaro reports that financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Vincenzo Lomonaco reports that financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available upon request.

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